

A Case Study in Kyane-Chaung-Gyi Village, Pyapon District, Ayeyarwady Region

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Abstract

This research focuses on the strategies for agriculture practices on economic anthropological point of view. Economic anthropology is the study of a system of production, distribution, and consumption of resources. The title of this paper is "the strategy for agriculture of Kyane Chaung Gyi village which is located in Bogalay Township, Ayeyarwaddy Region". The aim of the study is to highlight the strategy for agriculture of local people who faced with natural disaster (Nargis-2008). In this study, the data were collected by using qualitative research method including direct observation (DO), indirect observation (IDO), key-informant interviews (KII) and focus group discussion (FGD). Most villagers made living from paddy farming, fishing and trade. In the study of the agriculture of the village, many people who get income from growing rice have their own farms and some do not have. The expectation of the study is to find out the changes of agricultural practices and the way they would increase their system of agriculture.

Keywords : agriculture, farm, paddy, rice, practice

Introduction

Agriculture is a sector that holds great promise for pro-poor economic growth. Economic growth is a key factor for success. Enhancing the productivity and incomes of small holder family farmers is the key to progress. Agriculture also has significant linkage in its operations with other related sectors such as rural development, natural resource management, banking, insurance, media, governance, transportation and logistics management. (FAO, ITU,2016).

In other words, agriculture is seen as a key element of local economic development strategy, which would eventually reduce local poverty. More specifically, the common theme in many of these strategies is that local people should make the resources at their disposal work for them. Thus, land-based development strategies, including agriculture, among many others, are often seen as crucial to the development of local economies (Lahiff, 2002).

Myanmar comprises seven states and seven divisions: the Kachin State, the Kayah State, the Kayin State, the Chin State, the Mon State, the Rakhine State, the Shan State, the Sagaing Region, the Mandalay Region, the Magwe Region, the Bago Region, the Ayeyarwaddy Region, the Yangon Region, the Tanintharyee Region and Union Territories. The study area is located in Ayeyarwaddy Region., Pyapon district, Bogalay Township. This study site a Kyane Chaung Gyi village. As a country prone to heavy rainfall, floods occur regularly during the mid-monsoon period (June to August) in areas traversed by rivers or large streams. The country is also prone to cyclones, landslides, earthquakes, tsunami, fire and drought.

The Ayeyarwaddy Region being at the delta has abundant trees and forests and plays a significant role in Myanmar's economy. Its principle activity is rice plantation and it has been referred to as the barn of Myanmar's economy. Nargis making land fall in the Ayeyarwaddy Region, approximately 250 km (155 miles) southwest of Yangon. The cyclone affected more than 50 townships, mainly in Yangon and Ayeyarwaddy Region, including Yangon, the

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country's largest city and most important commercial centre. With wind speeds of up to 200 km per hour (124 miles/hour) and accompanied by heavy rain, the cyclone caused the greatest damage in the Ayeyarwaddy Delta region. The effects of extreme winds in this area were compounded by a 3.6 m (12 foot) storm surge.

In addition to rice, ground nut, sunflower, jute, beans and peas, sesame and corn are also cultivated. Locals of the study area are familiar with storms, since they live in proximity to the Bay of Bengal. However, one as intense as the Cyclone Nargis on 2 and 3 May 2008 which stormed through Ayeyarwaddy and Yangon Region has been experienced.

Prior to the Cyclone Nargis, the main livelihood the locals of the area were farming. However, after the Cyclone Nargis, there have been changes in the economy and lifestyle of the locals, having the farms destroyed by the sea water. Kyane Chaung Gyi village is situated in Bogalay Township, Pyapon District, Ayeyarwaddy region and is close to the sea, it is exposed to natural disasters such as floods and storms which are not unfamiliar to the area. However, the Cyclone Nargis of 2008 was the strongest one with the highest death toll. There are total 500 acres paddy fields in the village.

Economy of Kyane Chaung Gyi village was based on farming and fishery prior to the Cyclone Nargis. Livestock breeding of chicken, ducks, pigs, and goats were also done for domestic consumption. In doing so, the villagers used to have an adequate income for the survival of their family before the Cyclone Nargis. However, the Cyclone hit them hard where many died, buildings destroyed, and their livelihood suffered. In this paper, the study will be focused upon their strategy for agriculture. And, this research will express to compare about the paddy farming before and after Cyclone Nargis.

Methodology

The research is descriptive study design. To collect data, qualitative method includes library survey, Direct observation (DO), Indirect observation (IO), Key-informant interview (KII), and Focus group discussion (FGD) were done. (KII) was done with head of village, the owner of paddy field. Key informants who have the knowledge about the history and economy of Kyane Chaung Gyi village were asked. There are four key informants. The people mainly interviewed consist of the head of the village who perfectly know the situations before the Nargis and the later conditions after the Nargis and then a man who has been a farmer since the time before the Nargis. Two focus group discussions (FGD) include seven persons who work on farmlands on earn their livelihood. In conducting focus group discussions with the farmers, the topics to be discussed consist of the activities on farm-lands before the Nargis, and current activities that are taking place. Direct observation was done during the cultivation and harvest period. Indirect observation was done at the farmer home.

Agriculture

Paddy farming before and after Nargis

Before Cyclone Nargis, paddy farming was only depended on monsoon at Kyane Chaung Gyi village, due to the fact that the region gets very little fresh water during the summer and Cold season months. During these months, most of the water in the region is brackish or saline.

Three types of paddy were grown; short-term paddy (*Eh Mahta*) (farming period is two and half months to three months), mid-term paddy (*ManawThukha*) (farming period is three and half months to four months), long-term paddy (*Bay Kyar*) (farming period is four months).

Farmers arranged the three categories in such a way that the paddy may be harvested at different times. Short-term paddies were harvested first and then the mid-term, and then the long-term, in that order. In doing so, there would be less wastage. Late harvest cause grains to fall and therefore a lot may be wasted. Fields were ploughed in the month of *Nayone*(May), using buffaloes. Ploughing was done twice a day, from 6:00 am to 10:00 am, and 2:00 or 3:00 pm to 5:00 pm. It took five days to plough the entire big plot, which comprised 16 smaller plots (20' x 20'); an acre having 20 square feet.

In addition to rice planting, one tin of seeds were to be produced for every acre of rice. For the short-term (*Eh Mahta*)paddy one bushel of seeds were put in a two basket jute bag and tied at the top and soaked in water overnight. Two bushel-sized bags were used for half a bag of seeds for the rice to be able to expand. The seeds were then spread on bamboo shelves and covered with hay for about two days. Water was sprinkled on them to humidify the grains. The same procedure was used for the mid-term and long-term paddy, but they were soaked in water for three days and dried on the shelves for five days.

Grains on the shelves were shuffled by hand every now and then and taken to the field bank. After that, the grains were put in a container which would hold half a basket of grains. Two persons were then needed to throw the grains all over the field. However, care had to be taken that there was no water in the fields. Should there be any, it must be drained away. Young seedlings would rot with the water plus the heat of the sun. In addition, the seeds were thrown onto the field with either one hand or both hands so that they spread evenly on all sides. If they were not even, the shoots might get stunted where seeds are thick. There was also some damage or waste caused by crabs or fish. Therefore, pesticides are fed onto the fields prior to the sowing of seeds. An alternative was to mix pesticides with broken rice and fed only when crabs and fish came. After that, the seedlings were under close watch for about 30 to 45 days.

The seedlings were plucked during the month of *Warso* (July) when there is sufficient rain to remain in the fields. The water need to be about 1 foot above the ground so that the roots will come off easily. The seedlings were held with two fingers between the leaf and the stalk. The procedure is known as '*PyoHnote*' (Plucking Seedlings) in Myanmar language, and those who do this are called '*PyoHnoteThamar*' (seedling pluckers). Pluckers used to earn 500 kyats per 100 seedlings. After that, the seedlings were tied into bunches called '*Myo Paw*'. In about a day or two, these bunches were taken to the planting field, carried by hand if the field was close by or on bullock carts if far away. The seedlings had to be planted within four days after plucking or else they would go bad.

Planters were hired to plant the seedlings. They would earn 500 kyats for 100 plants. Planting was done in two ways: sticking the plants into the ground by hand or inserting the base of the plant into the ground with a special planting stick. There would be at least 7 or 8 plants within 6 feet. Laborers were hired for 3,000 kyats a day to replant or refill the field when the plants became too packed or when they got carried away by the flood.

The long-term and mid-term paddy were planted first at a lower level where there would be over one foot of water and the short-term paddy were planted later at a higher level where there could only be about a foot of water. Observation period after this would be about 15 days. Depending on the rainfall, draining of the fields was done so as not to spoil the paddy.

This procedure would go on until the month of *Tawthalin* (August). It would take about 15 days for the buds to emerge at the top and another 15 days for them to mature. These buds would then bloom around *TaSaungMone*(October) to *Nadaw*(November) months. Should there be too much rain during this period, the blooms would fall and the grains would not yield well and there would be a lot of husk without grains in them. Should there be too little rain; the

colour of the paddy would be red instead of yellow. Up till the Cyclone Nargis, the region used to have regular rainfall and yield used to be good. Pests such as 'YwetLeik', 'KyaukHsoo' and 'KaukYoeAthee' would damage the paddy, starting from the month of *Nadaw* (December). At such times, help would be requested from Bogalay Agriculture Department for remedies.

Harvesting or reaping was done beginning from the month of *Pyartha* (January). Wages for harvest of one big field was 40,000 kyats. Sickles were used for reaping. There would be two or three persons taking charge or the whole family would join in. Workers were hired to carry harvested paddy at 3,000 or 3,500 kyats. Those who could not afford much would carry the paddy by themselves. They were tied in bundles or sheaves. The sheaves were carried to an open field where they would be threshed with the use of buffaloes. Yield per acre would be around 60 to 85 (*tins*) or baskets. Rice grains were carried to the farmers' own barns or warehouses. A portion of it would be sold at rice mills. Each farmer would have at least 700 to 800 to even as much as 9,000 to 10,000 (*tins*) or baskets in their barns. They would sell them out at a later period when there would be fewer people who sell rice and so fetch a higher price.

The Cyclone Nargis on 2 and 3 May 2008 which stormed through Ayeyarwaddy and Yangon Region has been experienced. Nargis was the worst natural disaster in the history of Myanmar, and the most devastating cyclone to strike Asia since 1991. More than 140,000 people were killed, mainly by the storm surge. Cyclone Nargis stormed in the Kyane Chaung Gyi village at 9:00 pm on the 1st of May and the wind speed rapidly increased. The tidal waves against the normal cycle rose higher and higher, flooding all houses, schools, and buildings. Many people lost their lives. In the hours after 4:00 am on the 2nd may, the storm subsided and by morning, the wind speed became normal again, and the tidal waves receded. Because of this fateful event, many people lost their lives and homes. The top surface layer of the once fertile farms, trees and forests were destroyed by the salty sea water. Pagodas, monasteries, schools and health centers were ruined.

Kyane Chaung Gyi village was one which suffered the greatest damaging and had the highest death toll. There used to be 623 houses and around 3,000 people before the cyclone, the data which plummeted down to two partially damaged houses and around 100 persons in the aftermath.

The farmers had to suffer economic loss from decrease in yield for about two years. As for social ties, many lost their families, relatives, houses, and business, so they moved away to other places. However, there were also some who stayed on in spite of their loss and kept on struggling for survival. Some families were fortunate enough to have all members survive and so they continued to stay on and resumed their business.

Cyclone Nargis destroyed homes

After Cyclone Nargis, the consequences of Cyclone Nargis 2008 led to lack of seedlings, damaged fields, lack of food for farmers, and deaths of draught cattle. Therefore, re-allotment of farmland had to be carried out by regional administrators. The process is based on original field banks, land-marks such as trees and others.

There were altogether 32 farmers prior to the Cyclone Nargis out of which seven lost their lives. Relatives and immediate family members of those who died: wife, children, or siblings get the land. Around 2 months after the Nargis, "**Htoo Foundation**" donated farming machines so that the remaining farmers could resume their work. Owners of 60 acres farmland were given one machine each. Those who do not have 60 acres had to share, that is, 1 machine per 60 acres. Cyclone Aid Organization also donated 2 gallons of diesel per acre. "**Htoo Foundation**" also donated *Eh Mata* and *Manaw Thuka* seeds, 2 (*tins*) baskets per acre.

In the same procedure as the time prior to Nargis, seeds are soaked in water and are thrown onto the machine ploughed fields. However, steps such as plucking and planting seedlings are skipped and the direct farming method (*KyehKhin*) since many of the laborers who used to undertake this had died or moved away and the remaining farmers were facing lack of funds. Close monitoring is done until the plants are full grown. Harvesting is done with the help of neighboring locals and with the help of cyclone refugee camps. Helpers earn 3,000 kyats as wages. Harvested are tied into sheaves by farm owners themselves or farm helpers. The sheaves are then taken to the threshing site. Farm helpers earn 3,000 kyats/day. Machines are hired for threshing and winnowing. Owners of the machine would send one or two operators with the machines. Farm owner had to provide meals for them. Threshing wages are in kind; 3 (*tins*) baskets of rice for every 100 (*tins*) baskets. There used to be 500 acres of farmland prior to Cyclone Nargis but only 250 acres of farmland are now left. Yield per acre is 60 to 70(*tins*) baskets.

To be able to resume farming in the area, Ministry of Agriculture distributed paddy seeds and the Department of Industrial Farming helped out with the plough of fields with machines in 2009. Moreover, some farmers plough fields with the machines donated to them. The fields were ploughed and planted as before where the seeds were soaked in water and thrown onto the fields. Plucking and replanting seedlings were not done anymore but the plants were planted directly in the fields. According to the locals, many steps from the past procedures were skipped because those stages need many laborers. There weren't too many laborers available at that time and farmers could not afford the wages.

However, when the shoots came out, farmers had to face the destruction of the shoots by a hoard of rats. Even when the shoots grew into plants, the rats would still persist with their destruction. Farmers tried to rid the fields of rats by using traps and pesticides but there were so many rats that their efforts were in vain. According to farmers, Nargis killed snakes and birds that prey on rats. Therefore, yield was almost nil in 2009. In 2010, the 2009 procedure was repeated. It has been gathered that around 300 acres of land were used for planting rice. Destruction from rats still persisted until the shoots came out. Villagers used pesticides and traps like the previous year, they also hired rat hunters but still yield was not satisfactory in that year either.

The same procedure was repeated in 2011. Around 300 acres of farmland were ploughed and planted. Rats came as before and the villagers resorted to the same methods to get rid of them. However, the snakes, owls and other birds of prey had come back to the region and thus yield was not as bad as the past years. In 2012, there were around 400 acres of land in the area. They used the direct planting as well as the plucking and replanting of seedlings as

they had done prior to the Cyclone Nargis. However, the flooding of saline water in the fields caused many difficulties for the paddy to grow well. It was well that the farmers did not have to spend much on fertilizers and labourers. Furthermore, they were using the seedling planting method. They hired laborers from those who remained and those from the neighboring local areas for planting the seedlings. They were hired on a daily wages basis, set at 3,000 kyats a day. If they come in groups or families, wages for working on a big field would be 25,000 kyats to 30,000 kyats.

When it is time for harvesting them use hired help like they did during seed planting. They hired laborers from those who remained and those from the neighboring local areas for planting the seedlings, on a daily wages basis, set at 3,000kyats a day. If they come in groups or families, wages for working on a big field would be 25,000 kyats to 30,000 kyats. For threshing and winnowing, they hire machines. They pay in as they did in the previous year; 3(*tins*) baskets for every 100 (*tins*) baskets threshed and winnowed. Yield from using the direct method is 45 (*tins*) baskets per acre and that from planting seedlings is 55 (*tins*) baskets per acre. Reconsidering expenses, the benefit is more or less the same because the seedling methods incur more expenses.

After the Cyclone, widows who owned land were given a buffalo each by the **Law KaAlin (Light of the World) NGO**. Two buffaloes were given to widows who owned a lot of land. However, widows without land and widowers were not given any. Widows or locals who were not able to grow rice could have relatives' plant rice for them, or they could rent the land out. The process is called '*Thee Sar*' in the Myanmar language where the person who rents the land would have the rights to all the produce they will have to give the agreed amount to the land owner. For this case, the land owner gets twenty bushels of rice per acre.

In 2013, 400 acres of land were planted. The direct planting method was used on half of the total rice planting area of the village. Villagers preferred to plough the fields using buffaloes. Only when there were not enough buffaloes, then the machines would be used. Reason for this was that villagers believed they could plough deeper with buffaloes because the machines would go only to about 3 inches deep. Rental for a pair of buffaloes is 50 (*tins*) baskets of rice. Purchase of buffaloes would save the cost of 50 (*tins*) baskets of rice. Machines were hired only when there was not enough time to finish farming in time, using buffaloes. Machine owner has to plough the field himself, and is provided meals by the land owner. The land owner also has to buy fuel for the machine. Operation charge was 1,200 kyats after every bottle of fuel is spent. When machines are used, two big plots were completed and the use of a pair of buffaloes would take 2 days to complete one big plot.

Farmers sold out their machines and bought buffaloes which would cost around 300,000 kyats for one. A used machine would fetch 600,000 kyats to 1,000,000 kyats depending on the durability. During this period, an NGO organization called **ACF (Action Centre Farm)** donated what is believed to be a cash book, which is something like a check book worth 100, 000 kyats. The villagers were told to show the book to seed dealers or at rice mills when they go to Bogalay to buy seeds. When they actually went to the rice dealers in question, they got 90,000 kyats or 95,000 kyats worth of seeds. Ironically, the seedlings they got would be of bad quality or they were not given seeds but ordinary rice only which would not yield well when planted. That was why when brokers came and offered 70,000 kyats for a book, they sold them and bought rice with the money they got from dealers they know well.

Furthermore, the **Department of Agriculture** donated 50(*tins*) baskets of seeds for every 100 acres of land. But the seeds were not suitable for the area with sea water in the fields. Therefore they also sell these seeds as consumption rice and bought seeds from the dealers they know well. They could fetch 5,000 kyats for a (*tin*)basket of consumption rice and

pay 7,000 kyats per (*tins*) baskets for seeds. The seeds from dealers are from the local fields of especially grown and stored as seeds. Then the seeds were sown and the seedlings were replanted as before with the help of daily wage laborers earning 3,000 kyats per person per day or families who earned 30,000 kyats to 35,000 kyats for working on one big field. Plants damaged by rats were refilled or replanted as before. After that, harvesting was done. However, if harvesting was late, yield would be less by 10 (*tins*) baskets. Like before, farmers had to tie the paddy into sheaves. Laborers were hired with the same wages as in the previous years. The sheaves were then put on carts called '*Soopahs*'. The paddy were then threshed and winnowed with hired equipment. Threshing and winnowing was done day and night because work done during day time would be approximately 100 (*tins*) baskets but by working both day and night would produce 200 (*tins*) baskets.

Growing from seedlings would yield around 60 (*tins*) baskets and direct planting would yield 50 *bushels*. The rice grains are then put in sacks and covered with hay so that the paddy would not dry out. When this happen the rice grains would get smaller and lose weight. *Eh Mata* rice is sold at 3,500 kyats per (*tins*)baskets; *Manaw Thukha* is sold at 4,500 kyats per (*tins*) baskets, and Bay Gyar at 6,000 kyats. Rice is taken to the mills in motor boats. Those who own a lot of land would keep 15 (*tins*) baskets of rice and those who own fewer acres would keep around 5 (*tins*) baskets as seeds for the next year.

In 2014, there were around 500 acres of rice fields. Number of farmers also increased to about 30. Short-term, Mid-term, and Long-term paddies were also grown as before the Cyclone Nargis. However, those who do not own much land could not grow long-term paddy because they take time to produce and profit return is slow. Costs also increase. 10 more bushels of rice are required for hiring buffaloes at 60 (*tins*) baskets Planters also charge 40,000 kyats. Therefore the farmers could not adhere to the seedling planting alone but have to use the direct method as well. Direct planting would yield 50 (*tins*) baskets per acre and seedling planting yields 60 (*tins*) baskets per acre. *Eh Mata* rice fetches 4,200 to 4,300 kyats per (*tins*) baskets, *Manaw Thuka* fetches 6,300 to 6,800 kyats per (*tins*) baskets, and *Bay Gyar* fetches 7,200 kyats per (*tins*) baskets. Those who rent the whole plot would have to pay the land owner.

Paddy Fields

'Soopahs'

Buffaloes for Farming

The yield of paddy

Years	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Acres	500	500	500	250	250	300	300	400	400	500	500
Baskets	85	85	85	70	0	10	20	55	60	60	60

The yield of paddy

Discussion

In Myanmar, Cyclone Nargis struck the Ayeyarwaddy Region in May 2008, ruining numerous towns and villages, including Kyane Chaung Gyi village. Many lives were lost, and great damage was done to the environment and economy of the village in general.

Over use of natural events and natural resources has been mentioned in Elizabeth W. Markson, Peter J. Stein, (1991). According to them, environmental factors have an impact on the economic base and social ties of a society. Similarly, in this study, after the Cyclone Nargis 2008, not only was the surface soil ruined but the damage caused by rats added to the sorrowful consequences.

Nanda (1991) stated that scientific knowledge and application of technologies are essential in agriculture for commercial purposes. Progress results when adaptations are made to the traditional patterns. Contrast in Myanmar, in the study area, farmers used to have draught cattle and buffaloes but all were lost during the Cyclone Nargis. The State government and NGOs donated tractors and farming equipment and farmers tried to adapt to the changes. However, the area being flooded by sea water during the Nargis brought about deterioration of the machinery and equipment to a state where they were difficult to repair. Frequent breakdown of machinery made the farmers sell them off and buy or hire buffaloes with that money. Adaptations to traditional patterns are thus observed in the study area.

Conclusion

The paper is the case study of the period before the Cyclone Nargis, farmers cultivated short-term, mid-term, and long-term paddy, using the planting technique and yield was around 60 to 85 (*tins*) baskets per acre. However, the surface soil was ruined by the flooding of sea water. Moreover, in the years 2009 and 2010, the paddies were damaged by hoards of rats. For about two years the rats kept on destroying so much that there were no seedlings left for replanting. In addition, lack of workers and funds led the farmers to change their strategy to throwing seeds. Only about 3 years after the cyclone were the farmers able to use both the direct planting and throwing seed techniques in combination. Yield from the throwing seed method was 50 (*tins*) baskets per acre and that of the direct planting method was 60 (*tins*) baskets. Before the cyclone the local farmers plant only the monsoon paddy but since the yield was good, there was not only enough for consumption but also some left for storage for commercial purposes. After the Cyclone Nargis, due to the damaging of surface soil by the sea water, the destruction of paddy and seedlings by rats, shortage of workers, and lack of funds, yield was only for consumption but no more for storage. Therefore the villagers' income is only enough to survive.

In the study of the business economy of the village, there are people who have their own farms and do farming. In farming, those who could afford hired workers. Those who could not afford hired workers do family farming only.

References

- Beth B.Hass, Elizabeth W.Markson and Peter J.Stein, 1991, Sociology, Macmillan publishing company, a division of Macmillan, Inc.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and International Telecommunication Union, E-Agriculture strategy guide piloted in Asia-Pacific countries, Bangkok, 2016.
- Lahiff, E, 2002, An Apartheid Oasis? Agricultural and Rural Livelihoods in Venda, Library of Peasant Studies No 20. Serena Nanda, 1991, Cultural Anthropology, Wadsworth, Inc. Liton Educational Publishing, Inc.